
The Role of Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Influence of the Use of Technology and Knowledge Sharing Towards Performance Improvement Village Apparatus

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to determine the role of leadership transformation as a medium in the relationship between the use of technology, and knowledge sharing on the performance of village officials. This research uses a quantitative descriptive approach with primary and secondary data sources. The research population was all officials in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok, namely 196 village officials. Determination of samples using purposive sampling so that 100 village official informants were obtained. The research instrument used a questionnaire distributed using Google Form. Data analysis method using path analysis and with SmartPLS 4.0 as a processing tool. The results of this study indicate that the use of technology does not have a significant positive effect on performance. Knowledge Sharing significant positive effect on device performance. The use of technology has a significant positive effect on Leadership Transformation Knowledge Sharing significant positive effect on Leadership Transformation. Leadership Transformation does not have a significant positive effect on the Performance of Village Officials. Leadership Transformation is not able to mediate the relationship between the Use of Technology and the Performance of Village Officials, and Leadership Transformation is not able to mediate the relationship. Knowledge Sharing on the Performance of Village Officials in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok.

KEYWORDS: Village Official Performance, Use of Technology, Knowledge Sharing, Leadership Transformation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of village economic development must truly rely on the strength of village communities. The potential possessed by the village must truly become the root in the village's economic development. The potential of natural and human resources in the village must be a source of strength in developing the village economy. Programs between the central and provincial/district/city governments must synergize and strengthen existing needs in villages. The small environment at the village level is a driving force in the economic progress of the upper level community, this is of course influenced by the existing resources in particular Regency West Lombok is part of the NTB region which still requires attention from all levels Infrastructure, well-being, health, social and culture with a topography that varied moreover in the sub district Sekotong is one of the sub-districts in West Lombok out of 10 villages with the number of villages in Sekotong District being 9 villages whose existence is an asset in the southern part of West Lombok which has sufficient resource potential but still requires knowledge and information, especially in encouraging increased equipment capacity. Adequate village. Successful performance of Village Officials in the village in the subdistrict Sekotong provides satisfaction to the community. This can also have an impact on the empowerment sector and the economy. In the period between 2018 and 2022, there was a lot of work that should have been completed on time but was not completed, so this can be interpreted as meaning that performance was not achieved.

Good performance of village officials is village officials who are able to carry out tasks in accordance with their respective duties and responsibilities. According to Edison, et al (2018: 188) performance is a process that is referred to and measured over a certain period of time based on previously established provisions or agreements. Several research results show that performance is influenced by technology, work environment, and transformational leadership. Research results (Farooq *et al.*, 2021) shows that the use of technology has an effect on improving performance. Meanwhile, research (Alsaad & Almaamari, 2020) shows that technology does not always have a good impact on improving performance. Technology is not balanced with the exchange of information, giving results that are sometimes not good for boosting performance (Winkelhaus *et al.*, 2022).

Knowledge Sharing between fellow workers has a big impact in encouraging achievement transformation oneself towards higher knowledge and this has a positive influence on performance (Shamsi *et al.*, 2021; Setini *et al.*, 2020). Information can be

The Role of Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Influence of the Use of Technology and Knowledge Sharing Towards Performance Improvement Village Apparatus

provided Directly or indirectly, information obtained from information that is not optimal tends to make things negative and have a negative influence on performance (Lee *et al.*, 2013). The use of technology in performance is a process of increasing competence by humans and organizations in order to increase productivity and efficiency of work results based on development system systemic and systematic (Moenck *et al.*, 2022). Said by (Paranoan *et al.*, 2019), good use of technology can produce fast and accurate information so that stakeholders can make decisions efficiently without wasting a lot of time and money to verify the correctness of the information. for example, implementing a data warehouse in a company. Broadly speaking, technology also allows businesses to support external customer service efforts as well as assist individuals within the organization (Chadee et al, 2019). There are hundreds of platforms that streamline workflows but also facilitate work processes. Getting feedback is also easier because communication is also more efficient (Fernando et al., 2019). The impact of technological developments on business includes: The exchange and delivery of information becomes easier and faster because it can be integrated with each other. Apart from this, the use of technology does not mean that work can be completed quickly because the level of ability is still lacking, which is a negative thing in achieving performance (González, 2022). Technology is not difficult if it is balanced with personal abilities (Abbaset al., 2014), work completion will be slower if the adoption of work with technology is not trained to hone skills so that it actually becomes a source of decreased performance (Heslina & Syahrani, 2021).

Information sharing describes the exchange of data between various organizations, people, and technologies. There are several types of information sharing: Information shared by individuals. Can Find better ways of doing things. Building Community and Work Culture. Knowledge Sharing is one part of knowledge management in which a process of exchanging knowledge occurs between individuals in an organization/company. Knowledge Management enables individuals to stimulate innovation and change needed to develop organizations and fulfills many benefits for improving employee performance (Carmeliet al., 2013).

Continuously changing business needs (Kuzu & Özilhan, 2014). With faster access to information and resources throughout the organization, workers can act quickly (Ahmad and Karim, 2019). In relation to work in a company or organization, employees are required to be able to carry out knowledge sharing effectively so that the important knowledge obtained by employees can be spread evenly. Carrying out these activities in an organizational or work environment has Transformation leadership that identifies necessary changes, develops a vision that will pave the way for changes to be made and implements the plans necessary for these changes to occur thereby creating positive value in improving performance (Masa'deh et al., 2016). A person's leadership style in leading is very influential and is a determining factor for increasing and decreasing employee performance, therefore it is clear that every company needs an effective leadership style because in this case it also depends on the reliability and ability of the leaders.

Based on the description above from the findings of field phenomena, there is a research gap between usage technology and performance then share knowledge and performance, as well give mediated transformation leadership, the research title used in this research is "THE ROLE OF LEADERSHIP TRANSFORMATION IN MEDIATING THE INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGY USE AND KNOWLEDGE *SHARING* TOWARDS IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF VILLAGE APPARATUS (Study in Villages in the District, Sekotong, West Lombok, NTB)".

2. LITERATURE

2.1 Relationship between Variables and Hypotheses

2.1.1 The Influence of Technology Use on the Performance of Village Officials

The benefit of information technology is to support better human life because of technology information Can Help activities become more effective and efficient Runing *et al.* (2012), Amirudin *et al.* (2023), Information technology is a tool that uses computers that organizations or agencies use to work with information and support information and information processing needs for organizations. The measurement is based on utilization intensity, utilization frequency, and the number of applications or software used. (Sulasmining & Alliyah (2023) Appropriate use of information technology and supported by individual expertise operating it can improve company performance and the performance of the individual concerned. Several previous studies are in line with those expressed by Johnson (2012) Collie *et al.* (2012); Kraft et al. (2016); Ingersoll et al. (2014) has a good and positive influence on improving performance. Apart from that, Simbula et al (2011) explained that the use of technology can encourage interest in working in Taiwan. Based on theory and several previous researchers, it was formulated hypothesis as follows:

H1: The use of technology has a positive and significant effect on the performance of village officials

2.1.2 Influence *Knowledge Sharing* To Village Apparatus Performance

Knowledge Sharing positively influences the performance of village officials and employee organizations at five-star hotels in South Korea, findings (Hauet *et al.*, 2013). Submission Knowledge and technology from one department of the company to another can drive the evolution of new discoveries because it smooths the specialization of integration of knowledge resources and has a positive influence on business development (Pietro *et al.*, 2018). Li Researcher *al.* (2014) shows

The Role of Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Influence of the Use of Technology and Knowledge Sharing Towards Performance Improvement Village Apparatus

that quality *Knowledge Sharing* positively affects the manufacturing performance of companies in China. *Knowledge Sharing* provides information and provides access to external resources so as to provide stable sales growth with savings in exploration costs (Saqib *et al.*, 2017). Based on this description, the fifth hypothesis that can be developed in this research is as follows:

H2: Suspected *Knowledge Sharing* has a positive and significant effect on the performance of village officials

2.1.3 Influence of Technology Use against Transformation Leadership

Digital technology has changed organizations in irreversible ways. Cortellazzo's main findings *et al.* (2019); Adi *et al.* (2021), suggest that leaders are key actors in the development of digital culture, they need to create relationships with many distributed stakeholders, and focus on enabling collaborative processes in complex settings, while paying attention to pressing ethical issues, contributing to theoretically advancing debates about digital transformation and leadership (Karakose *et al.*, 2023) at high school level in Türkiye. In Findings (Karyotaki *et al.*, 2022) Use of digital technology, support for digital transformation, support for technology-based professional development. Based on theory and several previous researchers, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H3: The use of technology has a positive and significant effect on leadership transformation

2.1.4 The Influence Knowledge Sharing Towards Leadership Transformation

Knowledge Sharing provides information and provides access to external resources so as to provide stable knowledge capabilities with savings in exploration costs (Ashok *et al.*, 2021). Apart from developing the stock of knowledge, practice Knowledge Sharing develop creativity a leader in finding ideas more easily and creatively, in developing countries able to create an environment that allows for the transfer of knowledge (Mohammed and Zaim, 2020). Transformation of relevant knowledge to meet information needs regarding human resource development and increasing competency capabilities (Swanson *et al.*, 2020). Process Knowledge Sharing increase the tendency to self-promote so as to create new ideas (Al-Husseini *et al.*, 2021). Employees and leaders in any work environment can interact with each other Knowledge Sharing and will be able to exploit knowledge relevant to achieving performance goals in their environment. Based on theory and several previous researchers, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H4: Knowledge Sharing influential positive and significant towards Leadership Transformation

2.1.5 The Influence of Leadership Transformation on the Performance of Village Officials

In the digital era, leadership has a positive effect on organizational commitment, psychological climate, and ultimately will provide positive organizational commitment in the findings (Kawiana *et al.*, 2021). Shin's findings *et al.* (2023), Digital leadership has a direct and indirect positive effect on organizational performance. In addition, digital culture and employees' digital capabilities partially mediate the relationship between digital leadership and sustainable organizational performance in South Korea. Adopt leadership experts, supply chain management professionals, and organizational scientists in improving their employee efficiency through transformative leadership (Alkadash *et al.*, 2020). Based on theory and several previous researchers, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H5: The use of technology has a positive and significant effect on the performance of village officials

2.1.6 Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Influence of Technology Use on the Performance of Village Officials

Findings (Purwanto *et al.*, 2021) Transformational leadership has a significant effect on higher education performance, transformational leadership has a significant effect on innovative work behavior, and transformational leadership has an insignificant effect on the behavior of organizational members at universities in Banten Indonesia. Transactional leadership, transformational leadership, democratic leadership, autocratic leadership, bureaucratic leadership and leadership styles Charisma has a positive and significant effect on performance (Kadiyono *et al.*, 2020); (Mohammed *et al.*, 2020). Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H6: Transformation Leadership is able to mediate the use of technology on the performance of village officials

2.1.7 Leadership Transformation in Mediating Influence Knowledge Sharing On Performance Device Village

In the digital era, leadership has a positive effect on organizational commitment, psychological climate, and ultimately will provide positive organizational commitment in the findings (Kawiana *et al.*, 2021). Findings (Shin *et al.*, 2023) Digital leadership has a direct and indirect positive effect on organizational performance. In addition, digital culture and employees' digital capabilities partially mediate the relationship between digital leadership and sustainable organizational performance in South Korea. Adopt leadership experts, supply chain management professionals, and organizational scientists in improving their employee efficiency through transformative leadership (Alkadash *et al.*, 2020). Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H7: It is suspected that Leadership Transformation is able to mediate Knowledge *S haring* on the Performance of Village Officials

The Role of Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Influence of the Use of Technology and Knowledge Sharing Towards Performance Improvement Village Apparatus

Figure 1. Conceptual framework
Source: Author's preparation

3. METHOD

The research design is included in the explanatory research category (explanatory research). This research analysis uses quantitative and qualitative analysis. Meanwhile, the process of searching for data using the survey method used instrument in the form of a previously prepared questionnaire and spread via social media such as WhatsApp by creating link from google form to fill in data that will later be connected into google drive as a place for data collection. The measuring instrument used to measure variables in this research is a scale likert. Sampling to determine the sample that will be used in this research is based on purposive sampling. This research will be carried out on Village Officials and Village leaders in Sekotong District, West Lombok. This is based on the performance of Village Apparatus in the Village environment in the last 6 years in the District Sekotong West Lombok Regency experienced a decline in achievement experienced by Village Officials.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Measurement Model Test

4.1.1 Parameter Significance

A small significance value indicates that the indicator can measure or explain the construct significantly (Hair et al., 2010: 708). An indicator is said to be significant at an error level of 0.05, if P Value is smaller than 0.05. The results of the parameter significance test obtained a P value smaller than 0.05 for all indicators, meaning that all indicators can measure the construct significantly. P value each indicator is shown in Table 1.

4.1.2 Loading factor

Mark loading factor shows the relationship between indicators and their latent constructs. Mark Loading factor A high level indicates that the indicator is able to explain the latent construct well. Mark loading factor ideally a value of 0.7 or higher (Ghozali and Latan, 2012:78). Mark *loading factor* each indicator is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Construct Validity

Construct	Indicators / Items	P value	loading factor	AVE	CR
Use of Technology (X1)	X11	<0.000	0.730	0.586	0.887
	X12	<0.000	0.776		
	X13	<0.000	0.760		
	X14	<0.000	0.711		
	X15	<0.000	0.776		
Knowledge Sharing (X2)	X16	<0.000	0.759	0.569	0.887
	X21	<0.000	0.677		
	X22	<0.000	0.729		
	X23	<0.000	0.763		
	X24	<0.000	0.831		
	X25	<0.000	0.780		

The Role of Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Influence of the Use of Technology and Knowledge Sharing Towards Performance Improvement Village Apparatus

Leadership Transformation (Y1)	X26	<0.000	0.730	0.661	0.854
	Y11	<0.000	0.779		
	Y12	<0.000	0.816		
Village Apparatus Performance (Y2)	Y13	<0.000	0.842	0.647	0.928
	Y21	<0.000	0.787		
	And 22	<0.000	0.780		
	Y23	<0.000	0.732		
	Y24	<0.000	0.839		
	Y25	<0.000	0.867		
	Y26	<0.000	0.850		
Y27	<0.000	0.788			

Source: SmartPLS Analysis Results, 2024

In the initial stages of research, a loading factor value of 0.5 – 0.6 was still considered sufficient. Based on the loading factor estimation results in Table 5.6, it can be seen that the item values produced by the use of technology, knowledge sharing, leadership transformation, and the performance of village officials have met the convergent validity standard value because the loading factor value is greater than 0.5. So it can be concluded that the 22 construct indicators used in the research can be said to be valid.

4.1.3 Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

AVE shows the level of convergence of all indicators on the latent construct being measured. AVE values above 0.5 indicate convergence which is adequate (Hair *et al.*, 2010: 709). The research results in Table 5.6 show that the AVE value for each construct is below 0.5, which means that all constructs lack adequate convergence. Fornell and Larcker (1981) states that if AVE is less than 0.5, but composite *reliability* higher than 0.6, then the construct's convergent validity is still considered adequate.

4.1.4 Construct Reliability (CR)

In research of a nature exploratory mark construct *reliability* still allowed between 0.60 – 0.70. The CR value shows internal consistency, CR value above 0.6 reflects good reliability (Hair *et al.*, 2010: 710). The research results show that the CR value of each construct is the same as and above 0.6. This means that all indicators consistently reflect the same latent construct. The CR value of each construct is shown in Table 3.

4.1.5 Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity measures the extent to which a construct is different from other constructs. Thus, high discriminant validity indicates that a construct is unique and explains phenomena that are not explained by other constructs. Discriminant validity testing can be done by comparing coefficient $\sqrt{AVE}$ (or *Square root Average Variance Extracted*) each variable with the correlation value between the variables in the model. Something Construction is said to have good discriminate validity, if the roots $\sqrt{AVE}$ (or *Square root Average Variance Extracted*) is greater than the correlation value between variables in the research model (Hair *et al.*, 2010: 710). The discriminant validity test is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Discriminant Validity

Konstruk	AVE	$\sqrt{AVE}$	Knowledge Sharing	Performance of Village Officials	Use of Technology	Leadership Transformation
Knowledge Sharing	0,569	0,754				
Performance of Village Officials	0,647	0,804	1,024			
Use of Technology	0,586	0,765	0,745	0,99		
Leadership Transformation	0,661	0,813	0,980	0,880	0,730	

Source: PLS analysis results, 2023

Based on Table 4, the research results show that the root AVE ($\sqrt{AVE}$ or *Square root Average Variance Extracted*) technology uses variables, *knowledge sharing*, transformational leadership, and the performance of village officials is greater than the correlation value between variables in the research model. This shows that it has good **discriminant** validity.

The Role of Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Influence of the Use of Technology and Knowledge Sharing Towards Performance Improvement Village Apparatus

Structural Model Test

The structural model test is a measurement to evaluate the level of accuracy of the model in the research as a whole. Structural model testing is carried out through several approaches including: *R-Square*, *Q-Square Predictive Relevance*, *Goodness of Fit*, analysis path, and analysis of mediation effects.

4.1.6 R-Square

R-Square shows the strength and weakness of the influence that the dependent variable has on the independent variable. *R-Square* Also Show strong weakness of a research model. According to Chin (Lathan and Ghozali, 2012:85), value *R-Square* of 0.67 is classified as a strong model, 0.33 is a moderate model, and 0.19 is classified as a weak model.

Table 6. R-Square

Construct	R-Square
<i>Performance of Village Officials</i>	0,845
<i>Leadership Transformation</i>	0,657
Average	0,845

Source: SmartPLS analysis results, 2024

Table 6 shows that valueR2 Transformation Leadership is 0.657, based on the criteria of Ghozali and Latan (2012: 85), this model includes moderate model criteria, meaning variations in the use of technology and Knowledge Sharing explain Leadership Transformation Amounting to 0.657 percent, the remaining 34.3 percent is explained by variations in other variables outside the model. Meanwhile, the performance of Village Officials has valueR-Square of 0.845 or including a moderate model, meaning variation Usage Technology, Knowledge Sharing and Leadership Transformation able to explain variations in Village Official Performance of 0.845 The remaining 15.5 percent is explained by variations in other constructs outside the model.

4.1.7 Q-Square Predictive Relevance

Q-Square Predictive Relevance measuring how well the observations made provide results for the research model. Mark Q-Square Predictive Relevance ranges from 0 (zero) to 1 (one). Mark dQ-Square Predictive Relevance which is getting closer to zero, provides clues that the research model is getting worse, while on the contrary it is getting further away from 0 (zero) and getting closer to the value 1 (one), this means the model research is increasing Good. The criteria for the strength and weakness of the model are measured based on Q-Square Predictive Relevance according to Lathan and Ghozali (2012:85) are as follows: 0.35 (strong model), 0.15 (moderate model), and 0.02 (weak model). Formula Q-Square is:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R_1^2)(1 - R_2^2)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0,845)(1 - 0,657)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - 0,53165$$

$$Q^2 = 0.946$$

Based on these results, a value of 0.946 was obtained, which means that the estimated global model is included in the strong criteria, where 94.6 percent of endogenous construct variations can be predicted by exogenous construct variations.

4.1.8 Goodness of Fit

Goodness of Fit (GoF) measures the accuracy of the model as a whole, because it is a single measure of measurements router model and measurement inner model. The measurement value based on GoF has a value range between 0 (zero) to 1 (one). The closer the GoF value is to 0 (zero), the less good the model is, conversely, the further away it is from 0 (zero) and the closer it is to 1 (one), the better the model. The criteria for the strength and weakness of the model based on GoF measurements according to Ghozali and Latan (2012: 88), are as follows: 0.36 (strong GoF), 0.25 (moderate GoF), and 0.10 (small GoF) (Tenenhaus et al., 2004: 175). The GoF calculation from the analysis carried out using SmartPLS obtained a GoF of 0.692, meaning that the model is predictive within the strong model criteria.

4.1.9 Path Analysis

The path diagram structure is used to describe the relationship between latent variables, both exogenous latent variables and endogenous latent variables, indicators-indicators that form the latent variable. In hypothesis testing, H0 is rejected at an error level of 0.05 if the P value value < 0.05. Table 7 shows that:

The Role of Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Influence of the Use of Technology and Knowledge Sharing Towards Performance Improvement Village Apparatus

Table 7. Analysis Path and Significance Testing

Variable	Original Sample(O)	Sample Mean (M) (STDEV)	Standard Deviation (O/STDEV)	Tvalues	pvalues	Information
Use of Technology Village Apparatus Performance	-0.047	-0.048	0.080	0.586	0.558	Not significant
Knowledge Sharing Village Apparatus Performance	0.911	0.913	0.082	11.132	0.000	Significant
Use of Technology Leadership Transformation	0.315	0.334	0.087	3.609	0.000	Significant
Knowledge Sharing Leadership Transformation	0.555	0.540	0.098	5.647	0.000	Significant
Leadership Transformation Village Apparatus Performance	0.052	0.054	0.082	0.636	0.525	Not significant
Use of Technology Leadership Transformation Village Apparatus Performance	0.016	0.017	0.028	0.592	0.554	Not significant
Knowledge Sharing Leadership Transformation Village Apparatus Performance	0.029	0.030	0.047	0.614	0.539	Not significant

Based on Table 7, it can be explained as follows:

Use of Technology Positive influence on Village Apparatus Performance, produces a positive path coefficient of -0.047 with a t-statistic value of $0.586 < 1.96$ and a probability of 0.558 (significance level $< \alpha 0.05$), thus H1 is rejected. Testing the mediating role of Leadership Transformation on the relationship between the Use of Technology and the Performance of Village Officials needs to be carried out to find out if there is a perfect mediating role which causes the direct relationship between the Use of Technology and the Performance of Village Officials to be insignificant. Knowledge Sharing positive influence on Village Apparatus Performance, produces a positive path coefficient of 0.911 with a t-statistic value of $0.911 < 1.96$ and a probability of 0.000 (significance level $< \alpha 0.05$), thus H2 is accepted.

Use of Technology has a positive effect on Leadership Transformation, producing a positive path coefficient of 0.315 with a t-statistic value of $3,609 < 1.96$ and a probability of 0.000 (significance level $< \alpha 0.05$), thus H3 is accepted.

Knowledge Sharing has a significant positive effect on Leadership Transformation, producing a positive path coefficient of 0.555 with a t-statistic value of $5,647 < 1.96$ and a probability of 0.000 (significance level $< \alpha 0.05$), thus H4 is accepted.

Leadership Transformation Positive influence on Village Apparatus Performance, produces a positive path coefficient of 0.052 with a t-statistic value of $0.636 < 1.96$ and a probability of 0.525 (significance level $< \alpha 0.05$), thus H5 is rejected.

The results of the path analysis test can be explained in Figure 2 which displays hypothesis test results with significance values and path each hypothesis as follows.

The Role of Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Influence of the Use of Technology and Knowledge Sharing Towards Performance Improvement Village Apparatus

Figure 2. Hypothesis Test Results
Source: SmartPLS analysis results, 2024

Effects of Mediation

Mediation analysis in this research uses the examination method. Inspection method with how to do it twice analysis, namely analysis involving mediation constructs and analysis without involving mediation constructs. The results of the mediation test can be seen in the following image:

The Role of Mediation Transformation Leadership on the Relationship between the Use of Technology and the Performance of Village Officials

Leadership Transformation Perfectly mediates the influence of Technology Use on Village Apparatus Performance. Tested separately, the effect of Technology Use on Village Apparatus Performance Showed significant results ($0.558 > 0.001$; $\beta = 0.566$). When Technological

Transformation Included in the model as a mediator, coefficient path influence

Use of Technology against Village Apparatus Performance Decreased to a level where the relationship was not significant ($p < 0.525$; $\beta = 0.661$). This shows that it is not mediation Leadership Transformation In that relationship, so H6 is rejected.

The Mediating Role of Leadership Transformation in the Relationship between Knowledge Sharing and Village Apparatus Performance

Leadership Transformation partially mediating influence Knowledge Sharing to Village Apparatus Performance. Tested separately, influence Knowledge Sharing to Village Apparatus Performance Showed significant results ($p < 0.001$; $\beta = 0.569$). When Leadership Transformation

Included in the model as a mediator, influencing path coefficients Knowledge Sharing to Village Apparatus Performance Decrease But still significant ($p < 0.525$; $\beta = 0.661$). This shows that it does not play a mediating role Leadership Transformation In this relationship, so H7 is rejected.

4.2 Discussion of Analysis Results

Based on the results of the analysis described previously, each relationship can be explained with implications which are explained as follows.

4.2.1 The Influence of Technology Use on the Performance of Village Officials

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of technology use on the performance of village officials, a value was obtained with a path coefficient amounting to 0.586 with a significance of 0.558. Tested separately involving the mediating variable Leadership Transformation, it was proven that the use of technology had no effect on the performance of village officials. So it can be explained that the use of technology does not have a significant influence in improving the performance of village officials. Where the better the review of the use of technology in village officials, for example the use of online media, it is still unable to improve performance village officials.

The use of technology is a communication medium for sharing related information systems, new applications, or new information services or services that have been consumed by society. There are no positive statements regarding the use of technology communication which cannot increase the positive attitude of village officials towards products and services. New

The Role of Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Influence of the Use of Technology and Knowledge Sharing Towards Performance Improvement Village Apparatus

technology, such as the information system application used to provide KTP creation services, and others, is still not being used optimally because of ability and individuality in operating. Web services for promotions related to development programs cannot be delivered optimally to society because internet access is still not good. This research is not in line with research (Sulasmining & Alliyah, (2023); Johnson (2012); Collie *et al.* (2012); Kraft *et al.* (2016); Ingersoll *et al.* (2014), it is said that the appropriate use of information technology and supported by the expertise of the individuals who operate it can improve company performance and the performance of the individuals concerned.

4.2.2 Influence Knowledge Sharing On the Performance of Village Devices

Based on the results of the influence analysis knowledge *sharing* on leadership transformation, scores were obtained path *coefficient* amounting to 11,132 with significance below 0.000, which means that there is a positive and significant relationship between knowledge *sharing* on the performance of village officials. This explains that knowledge *sharing* the better it will improve the performance of Village officials in Villages in Sekotong District, West Lombok.

The relationship that exists between one officer and another in the Cendi Manik Village environment is already well established, information that has just been received can be spread well between one officer and another. Knowledge obtained either from the internet or other media can be spread evenly among village officials. This causes performance to be boosted well by the dissemination of information so that it provides impact positive impact on the performance of village officials.

This research is in line with research conducted by Hau *et al.* (2013); Peter *et al.* (2018); Peter *et al.* (2018), and Saqib *et al.* (2017), where knowledge sharing provides information and provides access to external resources so as to provide stable sales growth with savings in exploration costs (Saqib *et al.*, 2017)

4.2.3 The Influence of Technology Use on Leadership Transformation

Based on the results of the influence analysis experiential *marketing* to purchase *intention* earned value path *coefficient* amounting to 3,609 with significance below 0.000, which means that there is a positive and significant relationship between the use of technology and the performance of village officials. This explains that the use of better technology will improve the performance of Village Officials in Sekotong District, West Lombok. The use of technology will provide a digital leadership effect which means leader in Cendi Manik Village will have the ability of individuals or organizations to direct manage and optimize the use of digital technology in achieving business goals and creating added value. Digital leaders must have a strong understanding of technology, speed and ability to adapt to change, as well as the ability to motivate and inspire employees to innovate and achieve business goals through digital technology. Village leaders in the digital era must have the sensitivity and speed to see and assess changes and integrate this information into decisions in running their companies. This is because rapid technological developments have also changed the habits and behavior of village officials.

This research is in line with Cortellazzo's researcher *al*(2019); (Karakoseet *al.*, 2023);*et al.*, 2022), where the use of digital technology, support for digital transformation, support for technology-based professional development will have a good impact on performance.

4.2.4 Influence Knowledge Sharing to Transformation Leadership

Based on the results of the influence analysis knowledge *sharing* towards leadership transformation, scores were obtained path *coefficient* amounting to 5,647 with significance below 0.000, which means that there is a positive and significant relationship between knowledge *sharing* towards leadership transformation. This explains that knowledge *sharing* The better it will improve the transformation of leadership in villages in villages in Sekotong District, West Lombok.

Experience of a transformational leadership style will have the impact of a leader who awakens employees to think about prioritizing work and prioritizes the organization so that employees have trust and are motivated to do a better job. The behavior of leaders in Cendi Manik Village is calm and positive. This causes leaders to be more respected if they have a calmer and more positive attitude. *Knowledge sharing* carried out by leaders in Cendi Manik Village will open up good communication in whole component in the village. Transformation of relevant knowledge to meet information needs regarding human resource development and increasing competency capabilities among officials in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok.

The results of this research are in accordance with the results expressed by Mohammed and Zaim (2020); Swanson *et al.* (2020); Ashok *et al.* (2021), by Al-Husseini *et al.* (2021), which states that employees and leaders in any work environment can interact with each other knowledge *sharing* and will be able to exploit knowledge relevant to achieving performance goals in the environment.

4.2.5 Transformation Leadership against Village Apparatus Performance

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of leadership transformation on the performance of village officials, a value was obtained path *coefficient* amounting to 0.636 with significance below 0.525, which means that there is no positive and significant relationship between leadership transformation and the performance of village officials. This explains that the leadership transformation which will not have a good impact will improve the performance of village officials in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, and West Lombok.

The Role of Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Influence of the Use of Technology and Knowledge Sharing Towards Performance Improvement Village Apparatus

Transformational leadership which is very important is the leadership pattern of the village head where often village development goals cannot be achieved properly because the village head is less able to apply his duties as expected, because one measure of the success of the village head's leadership can be seen from whether the village government is able provide motivation to village officials so they can carry out their duties and his responsibility in accordance with the expectations and objectives of the implementation of the activities in question, so that existing tasks in the village are not neglected as in the implementation government, development and community as well as other activities such as administrative arrangements, bookkeeping systems, maintenance less than optimal service, less effective work discipline and efficient, if there are people who need services, they have to go to their homes, not the village office, there are even village governments who are not aware of their duties his responsibility as public servants they are often found in gardens or at sea. In circumstances like this, it shows that the village head is unable to apply what is inherent in him as a village leader. Because the measure of a village head's success in leading and developing a village is not solely measured by long speeches and briefings when there are events or discussions, but what is more important is dividing up the tasks given by him so that his subordinates will follow all the authority that is given to them. given. This is not in line with Kawiana's researcher *al.* (2021); Shin *et al.* (2023), son of Alkadash *et al.* (2020), shows that the adoption of leadership experts, supply chain management professionals, and organizational scientists in increasing the efficiency of there employees through transformative leadership.

4.2.6 Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Effect of Technology Use on the Performance of Village Officials

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of the use of technology on the performance of village officials through the mediating role of the leadership transformation variable, it was found that the results were not significant in the direct and indirect relationships. So it can be explained that leadership transformation is unable to mediate the relationship between the use of technology and the performance of Village Officials in Villages in Sekotong District, West Lombok.

The ability of individuals or organizations to direct, manage and optimize the use of digital technology to achieve business goals and create added value does not provide good interest in the use of technology. A transformation leader must understand that digital leaders are good leaders Another thing is knowledge, especially about the digital world. This is also an obstacle for leaders in Cendi Manik. The lack of infrastructure means that transformational leadership cannot maximize the use of technology to encourage improved performance of village officials.

Transformational leaders must to adopt and collaborating with the millennial generation in the digital era to aspire to the character of a national leader who is familiar with the touch of information and communication technology, friendly towards social media, and has a creative and innovative attitude, this has been done by the Village Head In the District Sekotong West Lombok as a person leaders but with changes in technology that require training, conditions do not support improving performance.

These results are not in accordance with Kadiyono's researcher *al.* (2020); Mohammed *et al.* (2020), transactional leadership, transformational leadership, democratic leadership, autocratic leadership, bureaucratic leadership and charismatic leadership styles have a positive and significant effect on performance

4.2.7 Leadership Transformation in Mediating Influence Knowledge Sharing On the Performance of Village Officials

Based on the results of the influence analysis knowledge *sharing* on the performance of village officials through the mediating role of the leadership transformation variable, significant results were obtained in the direct relationship and not significant in the indirect relationship. So it can be explained that leadership transformation is unable to mediate the relationship between knowledge *sharing* on the performance of Village officials in Villages in Sekotong District, West Lombok.

Channels that can be used to carry out knowledge sharing activities between individuals or organizations with various variants, for example via *Website, Facebook, WhatsApp, blog* or other social media. Transformation leaders are familiar with the concept that refers to the ability to manage an environment driven by digital technology. Village leaders have adapted to digital, are familiar with digital variants and are already sharing knowledge between individuals. Socialization has often been carried out in villages in the sub-district Sekotong West Lombok, it's just that the conditions cause it not optimally performance of Village Village Apparatus. These results are in accordance with Kawiana's findings *et al.* (2021); Shin *et al.* (2023); son of Alkadash *et al.* (2020), which states the adoption of leadership experts, supply chain management professionals, and organizational scientists in increasing the efficiency of there employees through transformative leadership.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This research has investigated the mediating relationship between technology use, and knowledge *sharing* on the performance of village officials through leadership transformation in Sekotong District, West Lombok. This research was conducted for overcome the gap between research paradigms that have been carried out previously. Research Contribution This is because existing theories are able to claim that there is a relationship between the use of technology and the sharing of knowledge on the performance of village officials. Meanwhile, the use of technology has a direct or indirect influence on the performance of village officials. Knowledge sharing is a factor important in supporting the achievement of Village Apparatus performance in West Lombok District.

The Role of Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Influence of the Use of Technology and Knowledge Sharing Towards Performance Improvement Village Apparatus

In order to encourage the use of technology and the dissemination of information, a leader has a major role besides having to be supported by infrastructure to encourage the use of technology in West Lombok.

5.2 Suggestions

This research has investigated the mediating relationship between technology use, and knowledge *sharing* on the performance of village officials through leadership transformation in villages in Sekotong District, West Lombok. This research was conducted for overcome the gap between research paradigms that have been carried out previously. Research Contribution This is because existing theories are able to claim that there is a relationship between the use of technology and the sharing of knowledge on the performance of village officials. Meanwhile, the use of technology has a direct or indirect influence on the performance of village officials. Knowledge sharing is a factor important in supporting the achievement of the performance of village officials in West Lombok District. In order to encourage the use of technology and the dissemination of information, a leader has a major role besides having to be supported by infrastructure to encourage the use of technology in West Lombok.

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The Role of Leadership Transformation in Mediating the Influence of the Use of Technology and Knowledge Sharing Towards Performance Improvement Village Apparatus

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